

An evaluation of nutrition and sustainability data capturing methods, uses and sharing practices across the UK supply chain - Milk as a use case

Summary

Climate change is accelerating with the effects becoming increasingly noticeable and severe. In response, the agriculture industry are transforming farming practices and the population is being encouraged to transition to a sustainable plant based diet. Huge amounts of data exist across the food system yet it is fragmented and the degree of data collection (and sharing) will vary across individual supply chains. It is important to understand the data that currently exists and how it interacts across individual supply chains. UK liquid dairy milk represents a short and almost exclusively domestic supply chain with a strong record of data capture and sharing from historical purposes of ensuring food safety and security of the milk supply. This use case aimed to map the environmental and nutrient composition data that exists across the dairy milk supply chain from (farm) production to retail to assess the data coverage, data collection methods and practices, data flows and transformations between stakeholders and attitudes to data openness. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with stakeholders across the dairy supply chain encompassing production, processing, retail and regulatory oversight. Interviews were held online from November 2023 to March 2024. Interviews focused on the data parameters held or collected by the organisation; the uses of the data; data sharing practices; the format data is shared in and it's storage; data quality and assurance practices; challenges in current data collection practices; and attitudes to data openness. Data maps were produced showing data capture, data flows and data transformations across the supply chain. A stakeholder workshop was then held to present these results and to co-develop standardisation recommendations for streamlining future data collection and sharing across the supply chain. Due to the significant progress already made in harmonising and streamlining data capture and sharing across the dairy supply chain, a set of general recommendations including learnings for other supply chains were developed instead. Overall, the dairy sector's data collection and reporting processes are well developed and successfully embedded into everyday practices. These recommendations may be applicable to similarly structured food chains with three stages (production, processing and retail) such as cereals and livestock supply chains.

Introduction

Climate change is accelerating with the effects becoming increasingly noticeable and severe ⁽¹⁾. The food system accounts for 34% of total global greenhouse gas emissions ⁽²⁾ yet it is also particularly vulnerable to the effects of climate change. The majority (71%) of food system emissions come from the primary production of food (on farm activities) ⁽²⁾ with changes in practices urgently required to mitigate the damage ⁽³⁾. Actions such as improving crop management, improving livestock management, altering supply chain activities and altering consumer demand for high GHG food products could mitigate impact from the food system ⁽⁴⁾. Compounding the need to tackle food system emissions, the global population is growing and is expected to reach 9.7 billion by 2050 ⁽⁵⁾ thus the food system will need to increase overall production.

Life cycle assessments (LCA) are used to measure the impact of an individual food or food product throughout its entire life cycle, from raw material acquisition through production, use, end-of-life treatment, recycling and final disposal ^(6; 7). LCAs are a useful policy and decision making tool to evaluate the environmental impacts of different practices, products and systems ⁽⁷⁾. Each LCA requires

the user to define the scope including the system boundaries which can lead to considerable variation in results and difficulty comparing. When considering the sustainability of food products, ideally nutrient composition should be incorporated as a function of the food product, as in order for a diet to be truly sustainable it must be nutritionally adequate. Nutritional LCA's have been approached in several ways including assessment of a single or multiple nutrients, incorporating nutrient indexes, and commodity-level scores incorporated into diet-level analysis ^(7; 8).

Many environmental impacts databases have been collated containing data ranging from agricultural commodities to food products ^(9; 10; 11). These databases quantify the environmental impact of foods using environmental indicators, the most common being greenhouse gas emissions. Each value is derived from numerous samples which may be taken across different regions or countries. Whilst valuable indicators, these databases currently don't have sufficient granularity to interrogate the impact of different practices or processes across the same supply chain. Differences in individual farming practices including feed choices, geographical region where the food product or ingredient is produced, and others can result in varying environmental impacts and nutrient composition of the same food products between different countries and even in the same country ^(12; 13). For example, the feed system for livestock impacts the nutritional composition of the final meat product with differing lipid profiles exhibited by grass and grain fed cattle, the latter being more favourable for health ⁽¹⁴⁾. Varying nutrient profiles and environmental impacts have also been shown in differing lamb production systems ⁽¹⁵⁾. In terms of dairy production, milk fat, protein and specific micronutrients composition are influenced by feed choice ^(16; 17).

Alongside the drive for more sustainable food production, populations are encouraged to transition from current dietary patterns which are heavily reliant on animal sourced foods towards more sustainable plant-based diets which put less strain on the environment and our natural resources. Yet diets cannot be truly sustainable unless they are also nutritionally adequate thus it is imperative that the healthiness of food remains central to public health messaging and that advice on sustainable dietary patterns considers nutritional adequacy in combination with environmental sustainability. Within the UK, an independent government commissioned review, known as the National Food Strategy was published to create a long-term plan to transform the food system into one that is healthy, sustainable and fair for all ⁽¹⁸⁾. Following this, the food data transparency partnership (FDTP) was formed which is a collaboration between government (DEFRA, FSA, DHSC), industry (GS1) and subject experts that aims to improve the environmental sustainability and healthiness of food through better and more transparent food data ⁽¹⁹⁾. One aim of the FDTP is to increase the transparency of environmental impact data, beginning with streamlining the measurement and communication of greenhouse gas emissions to meet net zero targets.

Huge amounts of data exist across the food system yet it is fragmented and the degree of data collection (and sharing) will vary across different individual supply chains. It is important to understand the data that currently exists and how it interacts across individual supply chains. Therefore, an individual supply chain, liquid dairy milk was selected as a use case. The aim of this work is to map the environmental and nutrient composition data that exists across the dairy milk supply chain from (farm) production to retail to assess the data coverage, data collection methods and practices, data flows and transformations between stakeholders and attitudes to data openness.

Methods

Research team/ collaborations

This project is realised through the collaboration of multidisciplinary representatives from the agri-food industry with in-depth knowledge of the food chain, government departments with relevant data and nutrition professionals with academic knowledge in conducting research. Co-incidentally, each of the involved partners are also stakeholders of the output (data maps) who can exploit these maps for their specific interests. The core research team was comprised of academics with expertise in nutritional composition from Quadram Institute Bioscience (QIB), government partners DEFRA and FSA, and industry (Dairy UK).

Selection of milk as a food chain

Liquid dairy milk was selected as a use case as it represents an almost exclusively domestic supply chain ⁽²⁰⁾ that is short and relatively simple. Data capture is well regulated due to historical food safety concerns ⁽²¹⁾ and to ensure security of supply.

Secondly, milk is rich in nutrients including calcium, vitamin B12 and iodine. Milk and milk products are an important contributor to the nutritional status of UK teenagers and adults (Table 1). Yet milk has a moderately high environmental impact ^(10; 22) thus transitioning towards more sustainable diets with less reliance on animal sourced foods is encouraged to mitigate environmental impact from the food system. The agriculture industry and supply chains in the UK are continually improving farming practices and supply chain management to transform the food system and become more sustainable thereby aiming to reduce the environmental impact of milk production over time. Milk presents an interesting use case as nutrition and sustainability need to be delicately balanced to avoid the unintended consequences of aggravating nutrient deficiencies or further driving global warming. Consistent data capture and coverage across the entire supply chain is key to monitoring these real-life changes and informing progress in sustainability and public health messaging.

Table 1. Contribution of milk and milk products to average nutrient intakes in the UK from NDNS ⁽²³⁾

Micronutrient	Adolescents (11-18 years)	Adults (19-64 years)
Calcium	34%	34%
Iodine	40%	32%
Zinc	15%	15%

NDNS, National Diet and Nutrition Survey

Sampling technique

Stakeholder groups across the stages of the supply chain (production, processing, distribution, retail) and relevant industry bodies were identified. These stakeholder groups were targeted through the research teams' professional network and invited to participate through email and informed about the study. In addition, at the end of each interview, participants were asked if there were any other stakeholders across the supply chain whom they wanted to recommend for interview, thus triggering snowball sampling.

Data collection

Semi-structured interviews using a topic guide were used to collect the qualitative data. The interview topic guide was developed by one researcher (LAB) and then shared with the wider group. Interviews with individual stakeholders were deemed the most appropriate method to facilitate data collection as they comprise a series of open-ended questions and ability to probe so that in-depth information could be collected about current stakeholder data collection practices and attitudes ⁽²⁴⁾. They are also convenient to conduct in a virtual online setting. Each interview was conducted by two researchers, one led the interview while the other took observational notes.

Prior to interview a draft figure of the detailed stages of the supply chain was developed beginning at the production stage with the cow being milked and ending at the retail stage when the bottled milk is sold. The inputs and outputs of each stage which affect the environmental impact of the product were also added (e.g., fertiliser, feed, water during the production stage). During the initial part of the interview participants were asked to view this map and suggest any further steps, inputs or outputs they felt should be added or changed.

Following this, interview questions focused on the data parameters held or collected by the organisation; the uses of the data; data sharing practices; the format data is shared in and its storage; data quality and assurance practices; challenges in current data collection practices; and attitudes to data openness. Given the primary purpose of the work was to develop data maps, particular attention was given to establishing which data were collected by each stakeholder organisation, any new data that were generated, and what data were received from other stakeholder organisations. The full interview guide is in **Appendix 1**. Interviews took place between November 2023 and March 2024 on Microsoft Teams. The interviews had an average duration of 63.5 minutes. Interviews were conducted by 2 interviewers, one led the interview whilst the other took observational notes.

Data extraction and analysis

All interviews were audio-recorded with permission from the interviewees and transcripts automatically generated by Microsoft Teams. Accuracy of these transcripts were confirmed by one researcher (LAB) and all data was extracted into a predefined template based on the sections of the interview. Results were extracted using a deductive approach (based on the pre-defined interview sections). Maps displaying each stakeholder and arrows indicating data that was shared with or by them were developed using Microsoft Powerpoint. Individual stakeholder slides were also developed displaying the data types, frequency and format of data received from others, data collected by themselves and newly data generated. Other insights including the uses of the data, data quality assurance practices, challenges with data collection, suggestions for improvements and attitudes to data openness were narratively synthesised from the data.

Co-development of standardisation recommendations

A hybrid stakeholder workshop was held at the end of the project (23rd September 2024) where all interviewed stakeholders were invited to attend. A total of 13 people attended the workshop (N= 6 online and N=7 in-person). The workshop had two key aims: 1) to present the use case results to supply chain stakeholders, 2) to co-develop a set of recommendations for streamlining future data collection and sharing across the supply chain. Due to the progress already made by the dairy supply chain in harmonising and streamlining data capture and sharing, a set of general recommendations including learnings for other supply chains were developed instead.

Box 1. Questions to guide discussion during co-development of standardisation recommendations

- Are we getting enough action for all this effort in data collection? How could we get more value from this data?
- What is the impact of the data that is being collected? Is there change in behaviour on farm in response to the data insights from data collection?
- Where are the missed opportunities for streamlining data collection and collation?
- What are the key indicators you think the industry/supply chain needs to be capturing and which indicators do you think are surplus to requirements?

- Data duplication and being asked multiple times for the same/similar parameter has come out of the interviews as an issue, where in your opinion is the most duplicated effort?
- Do you see a route for enabling data exploitation for policy design, implementation and industry monitoring without duplicating current data asks?
- We think it is quite evident that the dairy supply chain is a very well-regulated chain with a lot of data capturing and sharing evident- how can we reduce the fragmentation to create a more harmonised and interoperable data system which works for stakeholders from farm to retail and includes regulatory bodies?
- Finally, what would you like to see happen next?

Results

In total, N=11 interviews were completed with stakeholders across the supply chain. These included N=2 representatives of farmers (production stage), N=2 processors (processing stage), N=2 stakeholders who provide dairy support services (production and processing stages), N=3 retailers (distribution and retail stages), and N=2 stakeholders responsible for dairy regulation or trading (production, processing, distribution and retail stages).

The final map of the dairy supply chain including each step in the chain from milking the cow until the milk appears on a retail shelf is displayed in Figure 1. The inputs to and outputs from each stage of the supply chain which affect the environmental impact of the final product are also displayed.

Data maps were produced to track the reported data transfers between stakeholders. These were produced in a simplified format, without reference to specific stakeholders or companies where multiple exist (Figure 2). Figure 3 displays the data transfers in detailed format highlighting individual companies and named stakeholders as described within the interviews.

Figure 1. UK dairy milk supply chain

Figure 2. Overview map of data transfers between supply chain stakeholders

Figure 3. Detailed map of data transfers between supply chain stakeholders as identified within interviews

Uses of data

The data had a range of uses by different stakeholders primarily to produce progress reports, for economic reasons, to inform actions, for audits and compliance monitoring, and for benchmarking (Table 2). Farmers typically used the data to track the profitability of their business, satisfy requests from other stakeholders further down the supply chain or regulatory bodies, and to inform their management decisions on farm. Stakeholders involved in providing support services and regulatory/trading bodies cited monitoring compliance to health, safety and animal welfare

regulations and monitoring performance as an industry as their primary uses. Processing organisations typically used the data to advise farmers on actions they could take to reduce emissions on farm and to produce data insights by aggregating the data received. These insights were typically fed back to farmers in the form of reports, workshops and member websites/dashboards. Retailers used the data to produce reports, report to sustainability agencies and to benchmark progress of farms.

Data quality assurance practices

The individual data quality assurance practices employed by stakeholders are detailed in Table 2. In terms of quality assurance practices, for farmer stakeholders these varied from person to person. In addition, farmer stakeholders cited difficulty in ensuring all data captured is accurate as some farming practices are difficult to quantify *'Some of it is a bit of guesswork, some of it is quantifiable, but it's a bit of both really on that, um, it's easier to measure what you fed rather than what you've made ... because we weigh what we feed, but what we've actually made, we don't weigh it into the clamp. So there's a little bit of guesswork'* (S3). Processors tended to employ stringent data quality assurance practices within their data forms including plausible value limits, automated error messages, predefined units of measurement and mandatory fields. Once data are received by processors, outliers are typically manually inspected and data quality is confirmed through in person reviews to validate the submitted data. Retailer stakeholders tended to manually inspect data to ensure data quality by comparing to previous years data and then verify any outliers with farmers or farm carbon tool providers. Stakeholders involved in regulation or agri-support services had varying data quality assurance practices. Typically, data were manually assessed for quality and cleaned. A range of approaches were used to handle missing data including leaving them blank or gap filling using statistical or human logic approaches.

Challenges encountered and suggested improvements for data collection and management

Common challenges with data collection and management (Table 2) cited by stakeholders throughout the supply chain included manual data management, the time required to collect/manage data, varying data quality/accuracy between different stakeholders, and hesitancy from farmers in reporting data without prior knowledge of what it will be used for *'data without context can be incredibly damaging to the agricultural industry'* (S6). Stakeholder suggestions for improving data collection and management across the dairy supply chain centred around four interlinked themes: harmonisation, interoperability, simplification, and to advance science. There's a need for *harmonised* singular standards to be used around both individual measurements and overall environmental calculations. Whilst singular standards were mentioned, the viability of that was questioned with others stressing multiple solutions which are *interoperable* may be more practical. There was an emphasis on *simplification* to reduce the amount of data being collected and improve connectivity so that data could be seamlessly transferred to multiple stakeholders. These themes can be combined into a desired singular goal to create a singular central data system for data capture and management. This was mentioned by N=3 stakeholders *'I'd love somebody to have a massive great spreadsheet where I could put the whole lot into one spreadsheet and just say here you are... That would be my ideal'* (S3).

Table 2. Data uses, quality assurance practices, challenges and future perspectives of each stakeholder

Stakeholder name	Uses of data	Data Quality Assurance Practices /	Constraints in terms of data capture and quality	Suggestions for improvement
Trading body (S1)	Track progress as an industry. Produce annual reports for public and members.	<p>Define pre-specified data.</p> <p>Data received from milk recording organizations is pre checked.</p> <p>Manually identify outliers (values >2SD from the mean) and verify.</p> <p>Comparison to historically submitted values. Values with big variation are personally verified and any changes implemented that impact values documented.</p> <p>All quality checks completed before data is used.</p> <p>Missing data gets left blank.</p>	<p>All data reporting is voluntary. Time constraints associated with collecting, managing and reporting data.</p> <p>Data harmonisation and aggregation is a manual process.</p>	Employ a dedicated data management person
Retailer (S2)	Produce an annual report.	<p>Manual quality checking process and use of secondary data sources where available as references.</p> <p>Comparison to data submitted in previous years. Use Manufacture 2030 data from previous years to identify values that seem odd.</p> <p>Have aggregated benchmarks which enable easier identification of outliers.</p>	Time: manual data management in spreadsheets is a slow process.	<p>Move to digital platforms for easier data management.</p> <p>Need further digital solutions to support data collection and management across all supply chain stakeholders.</p>

		Missing values: try to fill gaps from other sources using most conservative (highest) value.		
Farmer (S3)	<p>Accounting purposes to calculate dairy costings per month.</p> <p>To apply for schemes / grants.</p> <p>To satisfy requests from downstream and regulatory stakeholders.</p> <p>To inform future farming practices.</p>	Ensuring accuracy of all data is difficult, some things are easy to quantify while other measures require some estimation.	<p>Time associated with collecting, managing and reporting data.</p> <p>Finding stable internet connection to use data collection apps whilst out on farm.</p> <p>Duplication: being asked to report same / similar data more than once by different stakeholders.</p> <p>Lack of recognition of length of time required to accurately complete a survey for a scheme and whether the reward (grant received) is worth investing that time.</p> <p>Level of detail required for data collection when not all farming metrics are easy to quantify. Sometimes resort to estimating the value as it's quicker than trying to quantify the real value or the real value could be a vague range.</p>	<p>Technological improvements to facilitate collection of arbitrary data e.g., automatically monitor solar panel usage, water usage.</p> <p>Singular data platform to enter, manage, and share specific data types with others.</p>
Processor (S4)	Aggregate data to advise members on emission reductions and present to farmers at workshops.	<p>Data units predefined in software.</p> <p>Auto verification limits applied to all fields in software so implausible values are flagged to farmer on entry.</p>	Heterogeneous data units: a lot of data reported by farmers is data that's been collated by others e.g., bank, feed company, who may use different units e.g.,	Making data collection and management more automated.

	Produce internal reports quarterly.	<p>Software doesn't allow missing data, farmer must fully complete form to submit.</p> <p>Area managers carry out manual inspections of top and bottom 10% of farms to verify accuracy of values.</p>	<p>fertiliser units of nitrogen per acre vs kg per hectare.</p> <p>Balancing data verification and data smoothing against true variability between farms and farming practices.</p>	
Dairy industry support service (S5)	<p>Compliance monitoring- use to alert FSA of food safety and animal welfare issues.</p> <p>To monitor rates of infectious disease.</p>	<p>Data is cleaned to harmonise terminology.</p> <p>Have an autogenerated exceptions report which alerts on cows where data events may be missing e.g., 35-month-old heifer with no report of having calved. These are then personally followed up.</p> <p>Follow ICAR standard protocols for capturing, storing and presenting data.</p>	<p>Varying levels of dedication from farmer in collecting continuous data.</p> <p>Labour shortages: lack of people to go on farm to take samples.</p>	Increased connectivity with online farm systems e.g., via APIs

Retailer (S6)	<p>To generate public sustainability reports.</p> <p>To report to banks regarding green finance commitments.</p> <p>To report to Business benchmark on farm animal welfare.</p> <p>To report to WRAP with environmental metrics.</p>	<p>Manual data checking procedure with carbon toolkit provider annually.</p> <p>Use standardised data variables.</p>	<p>Hesitancy from farmers. They are being asked for increasing amounts of data, and becoming more aware of data ownership and seeking assurances about how their data will be used.</p>	<p>Creation of tools to facilitate on farm decisions which recommend actions for farmers based on their carbon footprint results and will display the impact of taking said action on subsequent farm carbon footprint.</p> <p>Take holistic approach to farm data by looking at environmental data, natural capital on farm (carbon sequestration) and carbon footprint data together.</p> <p>Move towards product level carbon foot printing.</p>
Regulatory body (S7)	<p>To produce newsletter and for website.</p> <p>To analyse and compare competitiveness for export market.</p>	<p>Have predefined standard data units.</p> <p>Manual data quality checking using plausible limits.</p> <p>All outliers checked and may be personally verified.</p> <p>Missing data is gap filled using statistics or human logic based on other data.</p>	<p>Currently don't measure carbon sequestration on farm when looking at sustainability.</p> <p>Trust within the industry: farmers becoming nervous about providing data when they don't know how it will be used.</p> <p>Farmers understand their data has value so therefore its use should be dictated by them.</p>	<p>Streamline receipt of data through API's to improve speed.</p> <p>Harmonisation of farm carbon calculators.</p> <p>Central data system for all farm data to reduce fragmentation e.g., currently a dairy farmer who supplies milk to a processor and their bull calves to the meat industry may have to complete 2 carbon calculators.</p>

Farmer (S8)	<p>To complete environment agency audits.</p> <p>For Red Tractor farm assurance.</p> <p>To fulfil requests from processors and retailers.</p> <p>To inform farming practices and management decisions.</p>	Varies from farmer to farmer.	<p>Stable internet signal- poor connection means farmers cannot access apps / platforms for data entry and management.</p> <p>Labour shortages on farms for capturing data.</p> <p>Computer literacy skills in older generation of farmers as it is now a very technology-based job.</p>	<p>Reduce duplication for farmers - currently reporting the same data to multiple stakeholders.</p> <p>Simplify data collection by only measuring parameters that really matter.</p>
Regulatory body (S9)	To check compliance to food safety regulations.	<p>Forms have predefined data units for certain variables, others allow multiple data units.</p> <p>Data manually checked by 2 individuals.</p> <p>No missing data as missing's are flagged, personally requested and data isn't logged until it is fully complete.</p> <p>App uses drop downs and mandatory fields that cannot be skipped.</p>	Some data are not mandatory so rely on farmers to voluntarily provide.	<p>Scope for improving technology to streamline process, reduce errors and duplication of entering same data into multiple places.</p> <p>Central platform for managing data to reduce fragmentation.</p>
Retailer (S10)	<p>For benchmarking to identify most sustainable farms and those needing to improve.</p> <p>To inform prices for the milk.</p>	<p>Carbon calculator tool provider conducts quality assurance on data.</p> <p>Agriculture managers personally verify outlier values with farmers to ensure accuracy.</p>	<p>Data misreporting: difficult to separate what may be a bad farming year vs data manipulation or misreporting.</p> <p>Despite quality assurance processes there is still the possibility of human error and data anomalies.</p>	-

<p>Processor (S11)</p>	<p>To advise farmers on emission reduction options on farm.</p> <p>To inform design and development of Sustainability Incentive Model, which defines target actions on farms towards reducing emissions.</p> <p>To produce annual and ESG reports.</p>	<p>During data entry, system has autogenerated potential error message for significant outliers.</p> <p>External advisors manually check data for anomalies and errors and conducts on farm data validation visit.</p> <p>Manual checks by advisor are facilitated by the system which auto-flags potential errors based on ranges from the significant dataset.</p> <p>Following validation visit, data sent to Analytics Powerhouse which processes the data and runs further checks for outliers.</p> <p>Generally avoid missing data, in some cases it is possible to gap fill using available data.</p>	<p>-</p>	<p>Streamline the data input process to enable a more user-friendly / effective approach to inputting and using data to drive efficiencies, emission reductions and business gains on farm.</p>
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ICAR, International Committee for Animal Recording; IDF, International Dairy Federation; LCA, life cycle assessment; SD, standard deviation; WRAP, Waste and Resources Action Programme

Attitudes to data openness and possible concerns

All stakeholders felt that sharing aggregate data was valuable but emphasised data should not be fully open with N=2 stakeholders remarking on the need to retain control over the narrative accompanying the data. Value of open data was specifically noted in the ability to monitor trends over time, develop informed targets for the future, and demonstrate positive progress to others including investors and other stakeholders. Stakeholders involved in farming, agri-support services and representative bodies for the farmers and the industry (N=4) expressed their pride in the industry and were keen for data to be made open to publicise the progress the dairy industry has made in terms of the efficiency and sustainability of the UK industry. Demonstrating greater efficiency can result in better milk prices for farmers, one stakeholder felt farmers should get recognition for the efforts they are making towards sustainability. One stakeholder felt that data collection and open data were reflective of the new normal *'it's just the new terms of business really'* (S8) and highlighted the industry's progress.

Conversely, there was a general consensus that stakeholders held reservations and were reluctant for all data to be made open. Concerns centred on the risk of data being misrepresented or misused to publicly slander the dairy industry, in particular by tabloids or plant-based organisations (N=3). The commercial sensitivity of data was highlighted by a number of stakeholders (N=3), with concerns raised over the possibility of manipulating data for commercial gain. The variability of data accuracy and quality between farmers was also cited as a concern. To minimise the risk of data misinterpretation, it was mentioned that sufficient metadata detailing how the data were derived and quality standards should accompany all open data as *'Data without context is incredibly dangerous'* (S6). Two stakeholders discussed their concerns over data ownership and stated they would not expect access to data unless specifically granted it by the data owners. These stakeholders also cited their responsibility to be respectful of the person who provided or collected the data.

Recommendations for standardisation / Learnings for other supply chains

Overall, the dairy sector's data collection and reporting processes are well developed and successfully embedded into everyday practices. These recommendations may be applicable to similarly structured food chains with three stages (production, processing and retail) such as cereals and livestock supply chains.

- There are several *existing industry standards and ongoing initiatives* which contribute to the strength of this food chains data capturing and sharing processes. Primarily, the International Dairy Federation's (IDF) global LCA standard methodology for dairy; Dairy UK's initiative to harmonise results from farm carbon calculators by aligning all tools to IDF standards; and the Dairy Roadmaps work to drive industry action through setting targets for both processors and farmers. The IDF category rule set explicitly sets out how to allocate carbon and ensures comparability across the whole industry. Allocation across all food chains needs a defined standardised approach, including how to fairly allocate inputs in mixed farms.
- The method of capturing and verifying carbon data used by the dairy industry in Ireland is seen as 'gold standard' with a number of factors contributing to its success. These include the use of a single tool for assessing farm carbon scores, use of this same tool for benchmarking, government pressure on the dairy industry to meet their climate targets, and, the existence of a national food sustainability programme. In the absence of a single centralised data system in the UK, data harmonisation and improving the interoperability of tools that do exist are key.

- *Avoid and minimise data duplication.* Supply chain stakeholders, in particular, retailers need to ensure that they are using the data that is already available instead of asking for duplicate data in a different format.
- *Suggestions for how government can support supply chains and their stakeholders:* There is a need for a roadmap detailing carbon reporting priorities for the government and the order in which they will be tackled. Areas where decisions in approach are still required include; **1)** whether inter category comparison is required i.e., ability to compare steak to milk **2)** aligning methodologies for allocating carbon across multiple heterogeneous industries **3)** whether carbon impact should be linked to the nutritional value of the product or welfare or other ESG metrics.
- Future environmental data collection and reporting needs to expand beyond carbon to develop a more holistic view on environmental impact to avoid unintended detrimental consequences on water quality or biodiversity whilst striving for Net Zero. Indicators that represent overall environmental impact include farm nutrient balance (Dairy Roadmap) which is a good indicator of emissions, pollution, impact on water quality; birdsong (Dairy Roadmap) as a cost-effective proxy for biodiversity; and habitat types as an indicator for biodiversity on farm.
- Data transfer and sharing is working well but there is *still considerable burden on farmers who collect and report data* to multiple stakeholders. Stakeholders requesting data should pre-populate data forms with any data they already have from previous years to reduce burden and through linking up with existing data sources to reduce the effort required to report data and improve the integrity of the data received. E.g., BCMS data, livestock information data, access NMR data, allowing farm carbon tool calculator data to be used to pre-populate following year's form.
- AHDB have launched a data custodian initiative which aims to reduce duplication and the burden on farmers and streamline the flow of data across the supply chain. Under this project, farmers can share their data with AHDB in a protected account who in turn can share data with specific stakeholders at the request of the farmer and auto enter data into platforms or forms on their behalf.

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Appendix 1.

Stakeholder Interview 1 Questions: (Draft 1)

Introduction:

Firstly, thank you for agreeing to take part in this interview. The aim of this work is to develop a data map capturing all the sustainability and nutrition data that exists across the dairy food chain from primary production of milk on the farm to its point of sale as bottled or cartoned fresh milk.

Just to provide you with some background context before we begin, we know that cow's milk is a very nutritious product that's rich in iodine, vitamin B12 and calcium. It is an important contributor to the UK's nutritional status and in preventing deficiencies. On the other hand, the food system is responsible for 34% of global GHG emissions. Thus, for planetary health we need more sustainable food production to ensure we carefully balance reducing our environmental impact with maintaining nutritional status so that we do not aggravate micronutrient deficiencies in the population.

The dairy food chain is constantly undergoing transformations to improve its environmental impact so it is a continually evolving picture. We want to create a data map capturing all the sustainability data that exists across the dairy food chain so that we can visualise what data is collected across the chain, who collects it, the methods and processes used to collect the parameters, what the data is used for, if it is passed along to different sections of the food chain, what the data coverage in terms of environmental and nutritional parameters are across the chain and allow us to identify any gaps in the data that is currently being captured.

We want to emphasise here that we are not looking to access any data you or your organisation holds. Our aim is to capture the meta-data about the dataset- in other words we are interested in learning about factors such as what data you have, what parameters are included, who collects it and what format it is in, but we do not want to access it.

Does that sound ok? We will be recording this interview so that we can extract the relevant information from it afterwards. If you do not consent to this then we will not proceed. Is this ok with you?

Have you any questions before we begin?

Stakeholder information

Date and time of Interview:	
Interviewer:	
Name of Interviewee:	
Role and Organisation of Interviewee:	
Confirmation from Interviewee Interview can be recorded- Y/N	
Confirmation Interviewee is happy to take part in a workshop- Y/N	
Category/ Role of any other stakeholder(s) involved-	
What Stage(s) of the Food Chain would you say you / your Organisation represents?	

Confirmation of Stages of Milk Chain:

So, to begin, we have created a map of the stages of the milk food chain which covers its production on the farm to the point where it appears on shop shelves in bottled / cartooned form. In your opinion, have all the stages and Processes involved in the milk food chain been captured?

Share Visual Map of the stages of the food chain

1. Are there any stages in the food chain which you think should not be there? Yes/No. Please make comments.

2. Are we missing any stages/processes you think should be included? Yes/No. Please make comments.

Data Parameters and data collection

We mentioned we are interested in learning about the nutrition and sustainability data you may hold. Just to be clear when we describe nutrition data, we mean any data on the nutritional composition of the milk such as the protein, fat, calorie content of the milk etc.

When we say sustainability data we mean anything which can affect the environmental impact of milk production across the food chain. This may include information on use of feed, fertiliser, Manure Management, Fuel, electricity and other Energy, Enteric Fermentation, Water Usage and Quality, Air Quality, Biodiversity, Waste, or scope 1-3 emissions calculations

1. In terms of sustainability or nutritional composition data, do you / your organisation **receive** any data? (i.e. does anyone report data to you?) Internally or externally?
2. Is this data captured by yourselves or received from a third party? If 3rd party, from whom do you receive the data from?
3. How often do you receive this data internally or externally?
4. Do you / your organisation **collect** any sustainability / nutrition data?
5. What types of parameters do you / your organisation collect?
6. Who collects the data?
7. How often do you collect this data?
8. Is this data time consuming and resource intensive to collect?
9. Do you encounter any challenges collecting that data?
10. Do you / your organisation **generate** any sustainability / nutrition data yourselves?
11. Who generates the data?
12. How often do you generate this data?
13. Do you / your organisation hold scope 1, scope 2 or scope 3 Emissions data? ******(Scope 1 covers emissions from sources that an organisation owns or controls directly, **Scope 2** are emissions that a company causes indirectly and come from where the energy it purchases and uses is produced. For example, the emissions caused when generating the electricity that we use in our buildings would fall into this category. **Scope 3** encompasses emissions that are not produced by the company itself and are not the result of activities from assets owned or controlled by them, but by those that it's indirectly responsible for up and down its value chain. An example of this is when we buy, use and dispose of products from suppliers. Scope 3 emissions include all sources not within the scope 1 and 2 boundaries.) Scope 3 data includes Activity Data, Emissions factors.
14. Who calculates these scope emissions? Is there a tool used to calculate these?
15. Do you know how is this calculated? (Are there any estimates/averages/factors used instead of raw data?)
16. What are the drivers or incentives to capture sustainability data?
17. ******If stakeholder is not capturing sustainability data, what would incentivise you to capture sustainability data?

Uses of data

18. Do you require this data from your upstream suppliers or do your downstream suppliers require the data?
19. Once you have collected / received this data, do you change it / transform it in any way? Use it to calculate other information? Aggregate it? Y/N
20. Does the data aggregation process have a significant timing impact on the reporting process or data?

Data format and storage

21. If you / your organisation do not collect all the data yourselves, what is the format of the data received? (e.g., excel, csv file...)

22. How is the data received? By email, USB stick, paper, Shared Data Platform etc
23. What happens to this data after you receive it?
24. Where is the data you collect and the data you receive (if any) stored?
25. Do you have documentation that details how data is acquired, stored, processed, and transmitted throughout the organisation? This can include data collection mechanisms, databases, data processing systems, analytical tools, and data visualisation platforms like Power BI etc. If No, go to 27
26. Do you know who in your organisation might be able to provide us with this information?

Data Sharing:

27. Do you share any of your data with others or pass it to anyone else within the food chain?
28. In what format do you share the data? Do you share this in raw data form or do you aggregate / transform the data before sharing?
29. Why do you share the data? Are you mandated to do so?
30. How is the data shared or formally reported? I.e., by email, publish a report... other form?
31. How often is the data reported, published, or shared? Quarterly, annually?

Methods used to collect each parameter / data units

32. For each environmental and nutritional data parameter you have mentioned, do you know what the structure of each field is in the dataset? I.e. what is the unit of measurement for each variable? Just to remind you that we are not looking to access any data you or your organisation holds, we are just interested in the structure of each parameter.

Data Quality/Assurance

33. Are there any standardized methods for capturing the data parameters you have mentioned? Do you know if others within the food chain use the same or different methods for capturing the same parameters? Calculations of emissions, metrics, nomenclatures, measures etc? Sampling techniques, agreed estimations or apportioning etc?
34. Do you have any tools or IT systems used to capture or process the data? For example, calculators to get carbon footprint scores?
35. How is data quality maintained? Is it checked for errors? Is there someone in your organisation with responsibility for data quality as part of their role?
36. If yes, how often is the data updated?
37. How do you handle incomplete / missing data (if you have any)?
38. Is there a data assurance process?

Data Owner or Role of Data Collector or Processor

39. Do you have a team that is responsible for data capturing, data calculations, receiving the data? Are you (person(s) on the call) a member of that team? If not, can we have contact for someone from this team? No
40. Do you have a specific person in house whose role it is to look after sustainability data for your organisation?
41. What constraints are you/your organisation currently facing in terms of data capture and quality?
42. Do you have any suggestions for how you/your organisation could improve how you/it currently captures /receives/handles data?

Attitudes to Data Openness.

43. Where could you see value for your organisation by making sustainability data across the food chain open?

44. Would you have any concerns about data collected across the food chain being made open or being shared across the food chain?

Thank you very much for your time, I think you have answered all the questions we had for you today.

45. Have you any final comments or anything else you would like to add before we finish?

46. As we mentioned we are running a series of interviews with stakeholders from across the dairy food chain from on farm production of milk to where it appears as bottled milk on the shop shelf- Is there anybody else you would like to recommend that you think we should interview?

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